

The Impact of Liquidity Management on the Profitability Level of Pubali Bank PLC

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Abstract

This study investigates how liquidity management impacts the profitability of Pubali Bank PLC, a major commercial bank in Bangladesh. Focusing on the period from 2014 to 2022, the research relies on secondary data extracted from the bank's annual reports. Profitability is measured using Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), while liquidity is assessed using ratios such as cash ratio, cash to assets (CASA), and Net Interest Margin (NIM). The study employs regression analysis, correlation analysis, and descriptive statistics. Findings indicate that although Pubali Bank maintained a strong liquidity position, its profitability levels were relatively lower compared to other major private commercial banks. ROA and ROE were positively influenced by liquidity indicators, particularly CASA and NIM. The study recommends that the bank maintain high liquidity and implement strategic liquidity management practices to enhance profitability and manage liquidity risk effectively.

How Strong Banks Fuel a Stronger Economy: A Camel-Based Study of India's GDP

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Abstract

The banking sector is vital to a country's economic growth, especially in a developing economy like India. This study evaluates how bank performance influences India's real GDP using the CAMEL model, which assesses five core areas: Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management efficiency, Earnings, and Liquidity. Five banks each from public, private, and international sectors were selected using disproportionate stratified sampling based on market capitalization. Ten financial ratios from RBI reports and Moneycontrol.com were analyzed from 2021 to 2025. India's real GDP data was sourced from official national records. Multiple regression analysis reveals a significant and positive relationship between bank performance and GDP. The findings emphasize the critical role of a strong banking system in driving economic development and offer valuable insights for policymakers and regulators aiming to strengthen the financial sector's impact on national growth.